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COVER ART – The cover art was painted by Jason Poole and depicts a school of Mosasaurs.

A DROMAEOSAURID VERTEBRA FROM THE DINOSAUR PARK FORMATION (UPPER CRETACEOUS, CAMPANIAN) OF ALBERTA

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ABSTRACT - An isolated posterior dorsal vertebra of the dromaeosaurid theropod in the San Diego Natural History Museum found from the Dinosaur Park Formation (Campanian) of southern Alberta is described. The vertebra has morphological affinities to the corresponding elements of *Saurornitholestes langstoni*, although the lack of comparative materials as well as presence of minor differences tentatively precludes the referral of studied material to this taxon. The vertebra is reasonably well-preserved, so it allows for detailed comparisons with other dromaeosaurids. The vertebra is small, highly pneumatic, and parapophyses are located above the centrum. The combination of these features suggests a high metabolic rate comparable with modern birds was present in this dromaeosaurid taxon, and also indicates the presence of birdlike ventilatory air sacs.

INTRODUCTION

After the initial description of the holotype skull of *Dromaeosaurus albertensis* Matthew and Brown, 1922 from the southern Alberta which is now known as Dinosaur Provincial Park, many dromaeosaurid materials have been excavated within this area. *Saurornitholestes langstoni* Sues, 1978 was the second dromaeosaurid species recognized from the Dinosaur Provincial Park, and more than thirty years later a small dromaeosaurid taxon *Hesperonychus elizabethae* Longrich and Currie, 2009 was also described, based on materials found in this area (Longrich and Currie, 2009). An enigmatic theropod *Richardoestesia gilmorei* Currie, Rigby and Sloan, 1990, only known from fragmentary dentaries and numerous isolated teeth (Currie, 2005), is thought by some authors as possible dromaeosaurid theropod (Hendrickx and Mateus, 2014). The second species *Richardoestesia isosceles* Sankey, 2001, which is known from the Park area (Larson and Currie, 2013), is thought by some as a *nomen dubium* (Rauhut, 2002), junior synonym of *Richardoestesia*

gilmorei (Longrich, 2008) or might not be theropod dinosaur after all (Company et al., 2005). Although the cranial anatomy or tooth morphology of these Dinosaur Provincial Park dromaeosaurids have been described in detail (Matthew and Brown, 1922; Currie, 1987; Currie et al., 1990; Turner et al., 2012; Larson and Currie, 2013; Currie and Evans, 2020), the postcranial anatomy of these dromaeosaurids have been poorly described in literature due to lack of materials, especially vertebral column. *Dromaeosaurus*, *Richardoestesia* and *Hesperonychus* are currently devoid of any elements from the vertebral column (Currie, 2005; Longrich and Currie, 2009). Although Sues (1978) compared fragmentary vertebral remains within the holotype of *Saurornitholestes langstoni* with *Deinonychus antirrhopus* Ostrom, 1969, he only briefly described the morphological features of the vertebrae of *Saurornitholestes*. This work presents the first detailed osteological description of an isolated posterior dorsal vertebra of dromaeosaurid theropod found in the Dinosaur Park Formation in Dinosaur Provincial Park,

Alberta. Detailed comparisons with the vertebrae of other North American dromaeosaurids such as *Deinonychus*, *Bambiraptor* Burnham, Derstler, Currie, Bakker, Zhou and Ostrom, 2000 and other dromaeosaurids from Asia and South America provide several implications about anatomy, ecology and evolution of this Dinosaur Park Formation dromaeosaurid.

Institutional Abbreviations: AMNH, American Museum of Natural History, New York, USA; SDNHM, San Diego Natural History Museum, San Diego, USA.

Anatomical Abbreviations: di, diapophysis; hp, hyposphene; idf, infradiapophyseal fossa; ipf, infrapostzygapophyseal fossa; irf, Infraprezygapophyseal fossa; ns, neural spine; p, pleurocoel; pa, parapophysis; poz, postzygapophysis; prz, prezygapophysis.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The specimen described here was purchased by San Diego Natural History Museum from Charles H. Sternberg in 1921. The only available information is it was collected from the locality below Steepleville, Red Deer River of Alberta which is currently known as the Dinosaur Provincial Park (K. Randall, pers. comm.). It is probable that they were collected from the Dinosaur Park Formation (Campanian), as Sternberg investigated this area in 1910s and collected vertebrate fossils which are exclusive in Dinosaur Park Formation (Yun, 2020b; D. Tanke, pers. comm.). The specimen is also gray in color, which matches the condition of rocks in Dinosaur Park Formation that are characterized by their gray and brownish color (Eberth and Hamblin, 1993; Yun, 2020a). Considering that lower half of the formation is more gray than the upper parts (Eberth and Hamblin, 1993; Yun, 2020a), it is likely that the specimen described here was collected from lower or middle portion of the formation. $^{40}\text{Ar} / ^{39}\text{Ar}$ radiometric dating

constrains the age of the Dinosaur Park Formation, as a date of 77.3 Ma occurs in the uppermost part of the underlying Oldman Formation and 75.46 Ma occurs at the base of overlying Bearpaw Formation (Fowler, 2017). Given that the sedimentation rates for the upper 22 meters of the Dinosaur Park Formation and Bearpaw Formation transition were slow (Carr et al., 2017), the top of the Dinosaur Park Formation is likely slightly older than 75.46 Ma (Yun, 2020b). Numerous vertebrate fossils including fishes, amphibians, reptiles, dinosaurs and mammals have been excavated from this formation (Currie, 2005; Longrich, 2008; Yun, 2020a).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Due to the lack of funding at the beginning of this project, a high-quality cast made through 3D scan of the original specimen is mainly studied. The morphology of the specimen is compared with other dromaeosaurids such as *Deinonychus* or *Saurornitholestes*, using the conventional methods of comparative anatomy and assessments based on the review of the literature on dromaeosaurid anatomy. The anatomical nomenclature used in this study follows Ostrom (1969) and Sues and Averianov (2014). Sues and Averianov (2014) originally identified all of the dromaeosaurid elements from the Bissekty Formation as *Itemirus medullaris* Kurzanov, 1976, a taxon which is found by several analyses as dromaeosaurid (Longrich and Currie, 2009; Sues and Averianov, 2014). However, none of the postcranial elements described by Sues and Averianov (2014) were found with any braincase elements that overlap with holotype of *Itemirus medullaris*, which is a partial braincase (Kurzanov, 1976; Sues and Averianov, 2014). Moreover, there is a possibility that the holotype of *Itemirus medullaris* belongs to a tyrannosauroid (Holtz, 2004). Therefore, the postcranial elements described by Sues and Averianov (2014) are tentatively termed as “Bissekty dromaeosaurid” in this study.

SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

Dinosauria Owen, 1842

Theropoda Marsh, 1881

Maniraptora Gauthier, 1986

Dromaeosauridae Matthew and Brown, 1922

Dromaeosauridae *indet.*

Material: SDNHM 35589, an isolated posterior dorsal vertebra of a dromaeosaurid theropod.

Systematics: SDNHM 35589 is here referred as indeterminate Dromaeosauridae based on several key features including raised, distinctly “stalked” parapophyses, a centrum that is wider than long, and highly pneumatic nature of vertebra with large pleurocoels (Norell and Makovicky, 2004; Turner et al., 2012; Agnolin and Novas, 2013). Although SDNHM 35589 resembles the dorsal vertebrae of troodontids, it is unlike the dorsal column of that group in having large pleurocoels (Varricchio, 1997; Makovicky and Norell, 2004). Though some basal avialans also have stalklike parapophyses (Agnolin and Novas, 2013; Cau et al., 2015), SDNHM 35589 differs from them in having much larger size. Although a large troodontid taxon *Talos sampsoni* Zanno, Varricchio, O’Connor, Titus and Knell, 2011 is also reported to bear stalked parapophyses (Zanno et al., 2011; Agnolin and Novas, 2013), this taxon also lacks the combination of stalk-like parapophyses and large pleurocoels.

In Dinosaur Park Formation, there are currently four valid dromaeosaurid taxa recognized, including *Hesperonychus*, *Saurornitholestes*, *Dromaeosaurus* and *Richardoestesia* (Longrich and Currie, 2009). Based on its size, SDNHM 35589 belongs to a much larger animal than *Hesperonychus* which is less than 2 kg (Longrich and Currie, 2009). Currently, *Dromaeosaurus* and *Richardoestesia* are devoid of their vertebral skeletons (Currie, 2005) and SDNHM 35589 is indeed similar to posterior dorsal vertebra of *Saurornitholestes langstoni* described by Sues (1978) in overall morphology. However, SDNHM 35589 differs from the holotype of *Saurornitholestes* (Sues, 1978) in having proportionally much larger pleurocoels and smaller size, although these are highly variable characters (Turner et al., 2012; Brusatte et al., 2013; Sues and Averianov, 2014). Moreover, there may be additional dromaeosaurid taxa distinct from four taxa listed above (Currie, 2005). Lastly, no definite synapomorphies in dorsal vertebrae of Saurornitholestinae Longrich and Currie, 2009 have been recognized so far (Longrich and Currie, 2009; Currie and Evans, 2020). Therefore, it is best to consider SDNHM 35589 as Dromaeosauridae *indet.* in current status until the description of additional *Saurornitholestes* materials (Turner et al., 2012; Currie and Evans, 2020) as well as discoveries of vertebral materials of *Dromaeosaurus*, *Richardoestesia*, or any other taxa.

Figure 1. Posterior dorsal vertebra (SDNHM 35589) referred to *Dromaeosauridae indet.* from the Dinosaur Park Formation, Alberta. **A**, anterior view; **B**, right lateral view; **C**, posterior view; **D**, left lateral view.

Comparative Description: SDNHM 35589 (Figure 1) is assigned to posterior dorsal vertebra of dromaeosaurid theropod based on combination of small, anteroventrally positioned parapophyses on the lateral surfaces of neural arch, absence of hypapophysis, and narrow, raised morphology of diapophyses (Hwang et al., 2002; Burnham, 2004; Norell and Makovicky, 2004; Benson et al., 2012). The specimen measures 22 mm dorsoventrally and 22 mm transversely as centrum is measured on the anterior surface, 22 mm dorsoventrally and 21 mm transversely on the posterior surface. The centrum length is 11 mm at the ventral surface. The preserved neural arch length is 9.7 mm, and preserved neural spine is 8 mm long. The length of the centrum of SDNHM 35589 is very similar to measurements of the corresponding parts of *Bambiraptor* holotype AMNH 30566 (Burnham,

2004). Given that centrum lengths of dorsal series in dromaeosaurid skeleton are generally uniform (Norell and Makovicky, 2004), SDNHM 35589 probably belonged to an individual approximately 1 m in body length (Figure 2), assuming that *Bambiraptor* holotype is 1 m when complete. This is slightly smaller than assumed body lengths of *Dromaeosaurus* and *Saurornitholestes* (Longrich and Currie, 2009; Currie and Evans, 2020), although the apparent fusion of neurocentral suture in SDNHM 35589 may indicate an adult ontogenetic status of this individual. However, the degree of fusion of neural arch with centrum is problematic character in determining ontogenetic status as this character is either size-independent or individually variable (Brochu, 1996; Fowler et al., 2011).

Figure 2. Estimated size of dromaeosaurid individual based on SDNHM 35589. A, *Homo sapiens sapiens* about 170cm tall (Courtesy of NASA from phylopic.org); B, *Saurornitholestes langstoni* scaled after the size of SDNHM 35589 (Courtesy of Scott Hartman from phylopic.org).

The centrum of SDNHM 35589 is short, slightly platycoelous, and lacks prominent ventral keel. The anterior and posterior surfaces of the centrum are eroded, which reveal the honeycombed internal structure typical of theropods. Both surfaces are nearly flat with small concavities located centrally, although these could be due to erosions. The slight platycoelous dorsal vertebrae condition also occurs in *Buitreraptor*, *Deinonychus*, *Saurornitholestes*, *Variraptor*, and *Velociraptor* (Ostrom, 1969; Sues, 1978; Le Loeff and Buffetaut, 1998; Norell and Makovicky, 1999; Gianechini et al., 2018). In *Bambiraptor*, Bissekty dromaeosaurid and *Mahakala*, the dorsal series are amphiplatian (Burnham, 2004; Turner et al., 2011; Sues and Averianov, 2014). The overall morphology is spool-shaped, typical of dromaeosaurid dorsal vertebral centrum (Ostrom, 1969). The anterior surface of

the centrum projects more ventrally than the posterior surface. The centrum is taller than long, which is similar to *Austroraptor*, *Deinonychus* and *Saurornitholestes* (Sues, 1978; Gianechini et al., 2018). In small dromaeosaurids such as *Microraptor* or *Sinornithosaurus*, dorsal centra are longer than tall (Gianechini et al., 2018), and the dorsal centra in *Velociraptor* are long as tall (Norell and Makovicky, 1999). The pleurocoel is oval and deep, and situated anterodorsally on the lateral surface of the centrum. This morphology is similar to *Saurornitholestes* (Sues, 1978), although the pleurocoels in SDNHM 35589 are slightly larger. In *Deinonychus*, the pleurocoel is much longer (Ostrom, 1969). In some dromaeosaurids such as *Halszkaraptor*, *Mahakala* and *Utahraptor*, dorsal centra lack pleurocoels (Turner et al., 2011, 2012; Cau et al., 2017). The pleurocoels in SDNHM 35589

bear additional openings inside, similar to *Saurornitholestes* (Sues, 1978) but differs from *Deinonychus* (Ostrom, 1969). The preserved parapophyses are small, D-shaped, and raised on laterally projected peduncles. Similar morphology occurs in Bissekty dromaeosaurid (Sues and Averianov, 2014). In *Deinonychus* and *Velociraptor*, the parapophyses are larger and circular (Ostrom, 1969; Norell and Makovicky, 1999). Anterodorsal to parapophyses, the bases of prezygapophyses are preserved. The prezygapophyses are closely spaced as in *Deinonychus* (Ostrom, 1969). Small, subtle infraprezygapophyseal fossae present lateral to prezygapophyses, which is similar to *Buitreraptor* and *Velociraptor* (Norell and Makovicky, 1999; Gianechini et al., 2018). In Bissekty dromaeosaurid and *Deinonychus*, the fossae are much deeper (Ostrom, 1969; Sues and Averianov, 2014). The spinoprezygapophyseal fossa is ovoid shaped and deep, similar to *Saurornitholestes* (Sues, 1978). Both diapophyses are preserved, although the right one is better preserved. The diapophyses are excavated, similar to Bissekty dromaeosaurid and *Saurornitholestes* (Sues, 1978; Sues and Averianov, 2014). The preserved bases of diapophyses indicate these processes were narrow and slightly raised, similar to *Saurornitholestes* (Sues, 1978) but differ from *Deinonychus*, which has much wider and more raised diapophyses (Ostrom, 1969). Anteroventral to diapophyses, circular infradiapophyseal fossae are present. In *Deinonychus*, the fossae are triangular (Ostrom, 1969). Based on the internal structure of broken left diapophysis, the excavation of diapophysis and infradiapophyseal fossa are connected within the bone. The bases of postzygapophyses are preserved and the right one is better preserved. These processes diverge from the midline, and ovoid, deep, spinopostzygapophyseal fossa is present between them. In *Deinonychus*, the fossa is more triangular shaped (Ostrom, 1969). The neural spine is transversely compressed, and at least taller than the centrum. Its apex part is eroded away so it is unknown whether the

interspinous ligament scars terminate below the apex as in other dromaeosaurids (Turner et al., 2012). Ventral portions of interspinous ligament scars are preserved in anterior and posterior margins. In SDNHM 35589, hyposphene is extended ventrally from the medioventral surfaces of postzygapophyses, and separated by a midline cleft. Such horizontal, divided hyposphene is characteristic of some dromaeosaurids such as *Deinonychus* (Ostrom, 1969).

DISCUSSION

The dromaeosaurid vertebra specimen housed in the San Diego Natural History Museum is identified as Indeterminate Dromaeosauridae. It is identified as belonging to the clade Dromaeosauridae on the basis of its stalk-like parapophyses as well as presence of large pleurocoels. Its overall shape is most similar to *Saurornitholestes langstoni* from the Dinosaur Park Formation, but given that dromaeosaurid diversity from the formation is poorly understood, especially considering that there is a taphonomic bias that small dinosaurian taxa are largely preserved by isolated or fragmentary remains in the formation (Brown et al., 2013) so it is best to refer the specimen in this way. A more precise taxonomic identification of SDNHM 35589 will have to await more detailed description of postcranial anatomy of *Saurornitholestes* (Turner et al., 2012; Currie and Evans, 2020) as well as discovery of more dromaeosaurid materials from the Dinosaur Park Formation.

One intriguing feature of SDNHM 35589 is the highly pneumatic nature of the bone, as it bears large pleurocoels with additional internal openings, circular, prominent infradiapophyseal fossae, and hollow diapophyses. Given that SDNHM 35589 is from the posterior position, it is likely that nearly all dorsal vertebrae of this dromaeosaurid are highly pneumatized as in several other dromaeosaurids (Ostrom, 1969). The

postcranial pneumaticity in maniraptoran theropods has been suggested as evidence for highly elevated, birdlike metabolic rates (O'Connor, 2006) so it is very likely that this dromaeosaurid also had such metabolism as well as birdlike ventilatory air sacs. In some dromaeosaurids such as *Halszkaraptor*, *Mahakala*, *Microraptor*, *Sinornithosaurus* and *Utahraptor*, pleurocoels are missing in dorsal vertebrae (Hwang et al., 2002; Turner et al., 2011, 2012; Cau et al., 2017). It is not clear why the dorsal vertebrae of these taxa are not pneumatized. Given that halszkaraptorines like *Halszkaraptor* and *Mahakala* were semiaquatic animals (Cau et al., 2017) and increases in bone mass and density are common modifications in semiaquatic vertebrates (Ibrahim et al., 2014), the dorsal vertebrae devoid of pleurocoels in halszkaraptorines could be another adaptation for semiaquatic lifestyle of these taxa. However, the fully terrestrial taxa *Microraptor*, *Sinornithosaurus* and *Utahraptor* also bear non-pneumatized dorsals, and several basal dromaeosaurids like *Buitreraptor* and *Rahonavis*, pleurocoels are present only in anterior dorsal vertebrae (Gianechini et al., 2018). Therefore, the dorsal vertebrae devoid of pleurocoels could be merely a plesiomorphic character in dromaeosaurids, given that halszkaraptorines, unenlagiines and microraptorians are phylogenetically nested as basal positions within the clade Dromaeosauridae (Turner et al., 2012; Cau et al., 2017). If this assumption is true, then it is likely that SDNHM 35589 belongs to a derived dromaeosaurid.

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